

Comparative Study of Mangrove Species Composition and Forest Structure in Pandin-In and Myaw-yit Coastal Areas in Launglon Township, Tanintharyi Region

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Abstract

Mangrove forests are salt-tolerant forest ecosystem and they are formed when the marine water reached to the coastal area. A total of 13 species representing 8 genera and 7 families in the Myaw-yit area and 13 species representing 11 genera and 9 families in Pandin-In area were analyzed in present study. In the both study areas, Rhizophoraceae is the most dominant family, Avicenniaceae is the second largest family. Ecological successful species with the highest importance value were *Ceriops decandra* (Madama) 69.76% in Pandin-In area, *Avicennia marina* (Thame-phyu) 84.60% in Myaw-yit coastal area. The frequency gives an approximate indication of the homogeneity of a stand. In present study, high distribution values were found in lower frequency classes (A and B) whereas lower values were found in higher frequency classes (C, D and E). Where diversity indices for Myaw-yit area ($H=2.39$, $D=0.74$, $E=0.67$) was slightly higher than Pandin-In ($H=2.39$, $D=0.72$, $E=0.65$).

Keywords : Mangroves forests, Species composition, Importance Value Index (IVI), Frequency class and Species diversity

Introduction

The word "mangrove" is derived from a combination of Portuguese words for Tree (Mangue) and English words for stand of trees (grove). Mangrove Forest is also called a mangle. Mangroves are salt tolerance halophytic forest ecosystems of tropical and sub-tropical intertidal regions of the world (Tomlinson, 1982). These mangrove plants intake nutrients from the tidal sea water, river courses and the mangrove ecosystem, as such provide natural food to the mangrove dwelling fauna (Field, 1996). Mangroves are ever highly productive in vegetative reproduction and it can be seen as renewable natural biomass resources of the tropical countries. The estimated areas of mangrove forest in the world are sixteen million hectares (Field 1996). About 8.8% of South East Asia mangroves are located in Myanmar, of which 46% is located in Ayeyarwady Region, 81% in Tanintharyi Region and 17% in Rakhine State. Myanmar mangroves are reported as some of the most degraded or destroyed mangrove systems in the Indo-Pacific in which prawn and fish ponds are constructed since about 2000 (FAO, 2007). The diversity of mangrove species is higher in the world eastern group than in the western group. Diversity is composed of two distance components: (1) total number of species, and (2) evenness. An ecosystem is a major structural and functional unit of ecology. The structure of an ecosystem is related to its species diversity; the more the complex ecosystems, the higher the species diversity. The conservation of natural habit and the protection of biological diversity are important for sustainable development at levels ranging from the local to the global. Vegetation ecology includes the investigations of species composition and sociological interactions of species in communities (Smith, 1966).

These study will serve as a primary input toward monitoring and sustaining the phytodiversity and also would help in understand the threat that are being faced by the tropical forests and would help in deriving conservation policies. There is a lack of data on the depletion of tree species populations in mangrove forest in Launglon Coastal area. The quatitative inventory mangrove species diversity revealed a considerable variation in the composition of dominant specie and density in various forest areas. The objectives of the

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present study are to compare the species richness, species diversity, evenness and similarities among the three different study sites. The quantitative inventory of tree species diversity revealed a considerable variation in the composition of dominant species and density in various forest areas and the estimation of IVI have helped to understanding the ecological significance of the species, present in different communities. These findings may aid to the establishment of a regional baseline for improving management practices and environmental decision making.

Figure 1 Location map of study area

Climate

The climate condition of the study area is warm and wet tropical climate. The monthly mean rainfall for 2008, 2009 and 2010 are shown in Figure 2. According to the record, the area received maximum rainfall during July (970.28 mm) in 2008, during July (1692.46 mm) in 2009 and (982 mm) in 2010 while no rainfall occur in January, February, and December in 2008, 2009 and 2010.

The monthly mean relative humidity for 2008, 2009 and 2010 are shown in Figure 3. The highest relative humidity was recorded in May (95%) during 2008, in June (99.5%) during 2009 and in August (98.5%) during 2010.

The monthly mean temperatures for 2008, 2009 and 2010 are shown in Figure 4-a and 4-b). The hottest month was April. The highest mean temperature was 38°C in April 2008, 37.5°C in April 2009 and 39°C in April 2010. The monthly mean wind speed and direction data was monthly recorded for the year 2008 to 2009 are shown in Table 2.1. The recorded data show that the wind speed was high in June (2.9mph) directed southwest during 2008 and in July (3.8mph) directed southwest during 2009.

Figure 2 Monthly mean rainfall (mm) in Launglon Township (2008, 2009 and 2010)

Figure 3 Monthly mean humidity (%) in Launglon Township (2008, 2009 and 2010)

Figure 4-a Monthly mean low temperature (°C) in Launglon Township (2008, 2009 and 2010)

Figure 4-b Monthly mean high temperature (°C) in Launglon Township (2008, 2009 and 2010)

Aims and Objectives

- ❖ To evaluate the forest by quantitative analysis
- ❖ To clarify the tree species diversity
- ❖ To record the floristic composition and forest structure of each study

Methodology

Data Collection

Field data were collected during July, October in 2010 and January in 2011. A total of 14 sample plots (sample size was ranging from 15x15m to 20x20m) were laid down and studied. The diameter at breast height (DBH) and tree height (H) were measured. The diameter is to be measured using a diameter tape. Special attention should be given to the mangrove tree with stilt-roots, such as *Rhizophora* spp. where the diameter measurements was taken at 30cm above the highest root. All species with larger than DBH 5cm were recorded. The spatial location (latitude, longitude and altitude) of each quadrat was collected using a Global Positioning System (GPS). Water salinity of all study points were measured by using handy salinity meter ATAGO (S/Mill-E). Height measurement was done by a bamboo stick bearing a graduated scale was used.

Evaluation of density, relative density, frequency, relative frequency, mean basal area, relative dominance and important value index

The density of a species refers to the adequacy of its different requirements and the availability of space. Qualitatively, density of a species calls for its abundance in the vegetation or community. Density is determined by the following formula:

Density

$$\text{Density (D)} = \frac{\text{No. of individuals of the species in all the sample plots}}{\text{Total no. of sample plots studied}}$$

Relative Density

The Relative Density (R.D) of a species can be calculated with the help of the following formula:

$$\text{Relative Density (R.D)} = \frac{\text{No. of individuals of the species}}{\text{No. of individuals of all the species}} \times 100$$

Frequency

The frequency of a species is expressed as the percentage occurrence of its individuals in a number of observations. The frequency of different species growing in a community can be determined by-

$$\text{Frequency (F)} = \frac{\text{No. of sample plots in which the species occurs}}{\text{Total no. of plots sampled}}$$

Relative Frequency

For phytosociological purpose, it is generally expressed as Relative Frequency and is determined with the following formula:

$$\text{Relative Frequency (R.F)} = \frac{\text{No. of occurrences of the species}}{\text{No. of occurrences of all the species}} \times 100$$

Frequency is an easily assessable but important parameter of the vegetation study.

Basal Area

The basal coverage or the area covered by a species is used to express its dominant. The mean basal area of trees is calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Mean basal area (MBA)} = \frac{\text{Total basal area}}{\text{Number of trees}}$$

Relative Dominance

The Relative Dominance (R.Dm.) of a species can be calculated with the help of the following formula:

$$\text{Relative Dominance (R.Dm)} = \frac{\text{Total basal area of the species}}{\text{Total basal area of all the species}} \times 100$$

Investigation of Importance Value Index (IVI)

The overall picture of ecological importance of a species in relation to the community structure can be obtained by adding the value of relative density, relative dominance and relative frequency. This total value out of 300 is called Importance Value Index (IVI) of the species. The important value (IV) of any species in a community ranges between 0 and 300 (Curtis and McIntosh, 1951).

Species distribution by frequency classes

Raunkiaer (1934) formulated five frequency classes: Class A (1-20%), B (21-40%), C (41-60%), D (61-80%) and E (81-100%). These five frequency classes were used to determine whether the vegetation of the study area is homogeneous or heterogeneous.

Measurement of plant species diversity, evenness and coefficient of similarity

Species Diversity

Various species of plants and animals live in a community and exhibit species diversity. Out of the total number of species in a community, a few species are relatively abundant whereas a large percentage is rare. Common species are called as dominants. They determine the energy flow in a trophic system. Rare species determine species diversity. Ratios between the number of species, their biomass and productivity provide important information about a community and are called species diversity indices.

Species diversity indices are better measure of the species diversity of a forest and more informative than species counts alone (Weidelt, 2000). According to the Magurran (1988),

species diversity is often expressed by two indices, namely, Shannon-Wiener index (H), Evenness (E) and Simpson index (D).

Shannon-Wiener Index

$$H = -\sum_{i=1}^s (p_i)(\log_2 p_i)$$

H = index of species diversity

S = number of species

p_i = proportion of total sample belonging to the i th species

Simpson Index

$$D = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^s (p_i)^2$$

D = Simpson's index of species diversity

S = number of species

p_i = proportion of individual of species i in the community

Evenness

Two components of diversity are combined in the Shannon-Wiener function: (1) number of species and (2) equitability or evenness of allotment of individuals among the species (Lloyd and Ghelardi, 1964). A greater number of species increases species diversity, and a more even equitable distribution among species will also increase species diversity measured by Shannon-Wiener function.

The distribution of individuals among the species is called species evenness or species equitability. Evenness is a maximum when all species have the same number of individuals. Evenness was calculated by Shannon-Wiener function (1963), as follow:

$$E = \frac{H}{H_{\max}}$$

$$H_{\max} = \log_2 S$$

E = evenness (range 0-1)

H = index of species diversity

H_{\max} = species diversity under conditions of maximal equitability

S = number of species

Table 1 Location of sample plots in Myaw-yit and Pandin-In areas

Plot No.	Latitude	Longitude	Aspect	Coverage	Salinity
PDI-1	N 14° 11' 36.00"	E 98° 04' 43.80"	SW 225°	80%	2.8%
PDI-2	N 14° 11' 35.60"	E 98° 04' 45.0"	WSW 250°	80%	3%
PDI-3	N 14° 11' 12.80"	E 98° 05' 2.60"	W 270°	70%	2.8%
PDI-4	N 14° 10' 49.50"	E 98° 04' 46.50"	WNW 305°	70%	2.8%
PDI-5	N 14° 11' 16.70"	E 98° 05' 34.20"	WSW 264°	60%	3%
PDI-6	N 14° 11' 04.00"	E 98° 05' 39.20"	WNW 300°	70%	-
PDI-7	N 14° 10' 29.60"	E 98° 05' 42.80"	SW 240°	60%	-
MY-1	N 14° 04' 29.30"	E 98° 04' 36.90"	SW 245°	70%	1.5%
MY-2	N 14° 04' 31.00"	E 98° 04' 36.30"	SW 270°	60%	2.7%
MY-3	N 14° 04' 65.70"	E 98° 04' 85.70"	WSW 225°	70%	2.5%
MY-4	N 14° 04' 68.70"	E 98° 04' 84.20"	WSW 250°	50%	2.3%
MY-5	N 14° 04' 65.10"	E 98° 04' 77.10"	SW 240°	60%	2.3%
MY-6	N 14° 04' 18.50"	E 98° 04' 78.40"	NNW 345°	50%	0.05%
MY-7	N 14° 04' 81.80"	E 98° 04' 69.30"	NNE 20°	75%	0.04%
MY-Myaw-yit					
PDI- Pandin-In					

Results

Species composition and forest structure

An observation on species composition is one of the basic requirements to estimate the current status of the forest resources or to effectively plan and conserve the existing forest cover. A total of 805 individuals, representing 13 species, 10 genera and 9 families in Pandin-In area and a total of 1144 individuals, representing 13 species, 8 genera and 7 families were recorded in Myaw-yit area Figure (5, 6 and Table 2-a, b).

Figure 5 Mangrove species distribution in Pandin-In Area

Figure 6 Mangrove species distribution in Myaw-yit area

Table 2-a,b Ranking of dominant family by number of tree species composition in Pandin-In and Myaw-yit areas

(2-a)				(2-b)			
No.	Family	No. of species	No. of individuals	No.	Family	No. of species	No. of individuals
1	Rhizophoraceae	3	422	1	Rhizophoraceae	4	40
2	Avicenniaceae	2	113	2	Avicenniaceae	3	813
3	Euphorbiaceae	1	177	3	Myrsinaceae	2	90
4	Acanthaceae	1	2	4	Sonneratiaceae	1	143
5	Combretaceae	1	60	5	Euphorbiaceae	1	3
6	Sterculiaceae	1	3	6	Acanthaceae	1	1
7	Fabaceae	1	12	7	Combretaceae	1	54
8	Verbanaceae	1	11				
9	Malvaceae	1	2				
10	Leguminosae	1	3				
Total		13	805	Total		13	1144

Figure 7-a

Figure 7-b

Figure 7-a, b Ranking of dominant family by number of tree species composition in Pandin-In and Myaw-yit areas

In Pandin-In, the most numerous family was the Rhizophoraceae with 422 individuals represented by 3 species, followed by the families Avicenniaceae with 114 individuals represented by 2 species, respectively in (Table 2-a and Figure 7.a). In Myaw-yit area, Rhizophoraceae was the family that represented the greatest number of species 4, with 106 individuals, followed by the families Avicenniaceae with 813 individuals represented by 3 species, Table (2-b and Figure 7.b). According to this result, mangrove species composition was not significantly difference in two study sites. Taking 2 sites together, the family Rhizophoraceae and Avicenniaceae were dominated in study areas.

Importance Value Index (IVI)

The vegetation data were quantitatively analysed for density, frequency and mean basal area. The relative values were summed up to represent Importance Vale Index (IVI). Importance Value Index of 13 mangrove species in Pandin-In and Myaw-yit area were arranged in descending ordered as shown in Table (3, 4 and Figure 8-a,b). As the result of quantitative analysis, the highest IVI value was *Ceriops decandra* (Madama) 69.76%, followed by *Excorcaria agallocha* (Thayaw) 62.77% and *Avicennia marina* (Thame-phyu) 52.53% in Pandin-In. The highest IVI value was *Avicennia marina* (Thame-phyu) 84.60%, followed by *Avicennia alba* (Thame-kyettet) 75.37% and *Sonneratia caseolaris* (Lamu) 32.59% in Myaw-yit area. Based on IVI values, these species were found to be the most dominant species in the study area. The high IVI of a species indicated its dominance and ecological success, in the form of its better regeneration and greater ecological amplitude.

Figure 8-a IVI value of mangrove species in Pandin-In area

Figure 8-b IVI value of mangrove species in Myaw-yit area

Table 3 Ranking of Importance Value Index in the Pandin-In Area

No.	Scientific Name	R.D (%)	R.F (%)	R.Dm (%)	IVI (%)
1	<i>Ceriops decandra</i> (Griff.) Ding Hou.	45.34	12.12	12.30	69.76
2	<i>Excoecaria agallocha</i> L.	21.99	18.18	22.60	62.77
3	<i>Avicennia marina</i> (Forsk.) Vierh.	11.18	15.15	26.19	52.53
4	<i>Rhizophora apiculata</i> BL.	2.61	12.12	25.14	39.87
5	<i>Avicennia alba</i> Blume.	2.86	12.12	10.62	25.60
6	<i>Lumnitzera littorea</i> (Jack) Voight.	7.45	6.06	1.41	14.93
7	<i>Ceriops targal</i> (Perr.) C. B. Robinson.	4.47	3.03	0.99	8.49
8	Fabaceae	1.49	6.06	0.30	7.85
9	<i>Clerodendrum inerme</i> Gaertn.	1.37	3.03	0.11	4.50
10	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre.	0.37	3.03	0.24	3.64
11	<i>Heritiera littoralis</i> Dryand.	0.37	3.03	0.05	3.46
12	<i>Hibiscus tiliaceus</i> L.	0.25	3.03	0.03	3.31
13	<i>Acanthus ilicifolius</i> L.	0.25	3.03	0.01	3.29
Total		100.00	100.00	100.00	300.00

Table 4 Ranking of Importance Value Index in the Myaw-yit Area

No.	Scientific Name	R.D (%)	R.F (%)	R.Dm (%)	IVI (%)
1	<i>Avicennia marina</i> (Forsk.) Vierh.	42.01	18.92	23.67	84.60
2	<i>Avicennia alba</i> Blume	22.88	13.51	38.98	75.37
3	<i>Sonneratia caseolaris</i> (L) Engler	12.49	10.81	9.29	32.59
4	<i>Lumnitzera littorea</i> (Jack) Voight	4.72	8.11	12.95	25.78
5	<i>Avicennia officinalis</i> L.	6.11	13.51	4.37	24.00
6	<i>Aegiceros corniculatum</i> (L) Blanco	7.69	8.11	1.40	17.20
7	<i>Excoecaria agallocha</i> L.	0.26	5.41	7.29	12.96
8	<i>Ceriops dacandra</i> (Griff.) Ding Hou	2.36	5.41	0.48	8.25
9	<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i> Lamk.	0.44	5.41	1.28	7.12
10	<i>Rhizophora apiculata</i> BL.	0.61	2.70	0.22	3.53
11	<i>Aegiceros floridum</i> Rom & Schult	0.17	2.70	0.06	2.93
12	<i>Ceriops targal</i> (Perr.) C. B. Robinson	0.09	2.70	0.01	2.80
13	<i>Acanthus ilicifolius</i> L.	0.17	2.70	0.0002	2.88
Total		100	100	100	300

Mangrove species distribution by frequency classes

Five frequency classes of species frequency distribution found in the study area were shown in Table (5.a and b and Figure 9).

Figure 9 Mangrove species distribution by frequency classes in study area

Table 5.a Species distribution by frequency classes in Pandin-In area

Frequency Range	Frequency Class	No. of species	Total individual	% of total species frequency distribution
1-20%	A	6	57	46.15
21-40%	B	2	72	15.38
41-60%	C	3	409	23.08
61-80%	D	1	90	7.69
81-100%	E	1	177	7.69
Total		13	805	100.00

Table 5.b Species distribution by frequency classes in Myaw-yit area

Frequency Range	Frequency Class	No. of species	Total individual	% of total species frequency distribution
1-20%	A	4	11	30.77
21-40%	B	3	35	23.08
41-60%	C	3	285	23.08
61-80%	D	2	332	15.38
81-100%	E	1	481	7.69
Total		13	1144	100.00

The frequency gives an approximate indication of the homogeneity of a stand. In the Pandin-In area, only *Excoecaria agallocha* was found in frequency class E (81-100%) while *Avicennia marina* was found in frequency class E in Myaw-yit area. Only *Avicennia marina* belongs to frequency class D (61-80%) in Pandin-In area, and two species namely *Avicennia alba* and *A. officinalis* belongs to frequency class D in Myaw-yit area. In this present study, high distribution values were found in lower frequency classes (Frequency classes A and B) whereas lower values were found in higher frequency classes (Frequency classes C, D and E).

Table 6 Mangrove species diversity indices in two study areas

Diversity Indices	Pandin-In	Myaw-yit
Shannon-Wiener Index (H)	2.39	2.39
Simpson Index (D)	0.72	0.74
Shannon-Wiener Evenness (E)	0.65	0.67

The result of the species diversity indices, such as Shannon-Wiener (H), Simpson (D), and Shannon-Wiener Evenness (E) in Myaw-yit area (2.39, 0.74, 0.67) were slightly higher than Pandin-In area (2.39, 0.72, 0.65). So that mangrove species in Myaw-yit area was more equitably distributed than Pandin-In area as shown in Table 6.

Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, two sites were established to investigate the mangrove species composition, forest structure and assessment of plant species diversity. In Pandin-In area, 805 individuals were sampled, belonging to 10 families, 11 genera and 13 species. In Myaw-yit area, 1144 individuals belonging to 7 families, 8 genera and 13 species were recorded. In the both study sites, Rhizophoraceae is the most dominant family, Avicenniaceae is the second largest family. From this result, it can be seen that, mangrove species composition of Pandin-In and Myaw-yit areas were not significantly different, because the study area is similar to climatic condition (rainfall, temperature, moisture) and at the same ranged. Ecological successful species with the highest importance value were *Ceriops decandra* (Madama) 69.76% in Pandin-In area, *Avicennia marina* (Thame-phyu) 84.60% in Myaw-yit area.

The frequency gives an approximate indication of the homogeneity of a stand. In recent study, high value of species distribution were found in lower frequency classes (A, B) whereas lower values were found in higher frequency classes (C, D and E) in both study areas. In the present study, the mangrove species diversity in two different sites has been compared. The results show that Myaw-yit area ($H=2.39$, $D=0.74$, $E=0.67$) were slightly higher than Pandin-In area ($H=2.39$, $D=0.72$, $E=0.65$). This may be due to human impact is more intense in Pandin-In area. Pole, post, fences and fire wood collection were commonly occurred in Pandin-In area.

According to this study, it can be concluded that Rhizophoraceae Family in Launglon Coastal area is still rich in the plant species diversity in all areas but Avicenniaceae Family is rich in Pandin-In and Pan-Nyet areas but these family was very rare in Yan-Ma-Zuu-Aw. Maintenance of the diversity of species and habitats and sustainable use of resources are important to protect the points of future generation. Therefore, special priority should be given to manage the dominance Families such as Rhizophoraceae, Fabaceae and Avicenniaceae Families, which plays an essential role in the livelihood of the local inhabitants in this region. The objective of this study is to obtain the representative trees species from different study area, to evaluate the forest by quantitative analysis, to understanding the ecological significance of the species and to determine the stand structure and species distribution in different communities of Launglon Coastal area.

The direct values are production from mangrove forest comprising such as fuel wood production and fish and shellfish productivity conservation etc. Indirect values are effects by various forest functions such as biodiversity conservation, erosion and flood control and carbon sequestration (Forest Department and JICA, 2005). Therefore, ecological study at regular intervals is needed to monitor the survival and growth of plant species and habitat conditions. Moreover, monitoring of plant species may also be important in understanding the overall effects of restoration work. The baseline data on plant species recorded during the present study can be used for monitoring the environmental changes in future.

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References

- Curtis, J. T. and McIntosh, R. P. (1951). *An upland forest continuum in the prairie forest border region of Wisconsin*. - Ecology 32; 476-496.
- FAO. (2007). *Mangrove guidebook for Southeast Asia*. FAO Regional Office for Asia and the Indo-Pacific in which prawn and fish ponds are constructed since about 2000 (FAO 2007).
- Field, C.D. (1996). *Restoration of mangrove ecosystems*. International Society of Mangrove Ecosystem. Japan: Okinawa, Japan. 1-250.
- Lloyd, M. & Ghelardi, R. J. (1964). *A Table for Calculating the Equitability Component of Species Diversity*. J. Anim Ecol, 33, 217-225.

- Magurran, A.E. (1988). *Ecological Diversity and its Measurement*. Princeton University Press. New Jersey.
- Raunkiaer C. (1934). *The life from of plant and Statistical plant Geography*.
- Shannon, C.E., and W. Wiener. (1963). *The Mathematical Theory of Communication*. USA: University of Illinois Press, Urbana, USA.
- Smith, R.L. (1966). *Ecology and field Biology*. NewYork: Harper and Row.
- Tomlinson,P.B (Philip Barry). (1982). *The botany of Mangroves*.
- Weidelt, H.J. (2000). *Lectures Notes on Tropical Silviculture I and II*. Germany: Institute of Silviculture, Sec.II, Tropical Silviculture, Gottingen University, Germany (Unpublished).